

BRICS+ and the Construction of a Global De-Dollarization Agenda

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Abstract

The BRICS+ de-dollarization agenda has gained prominence in the international arena as it seeks to strengthen the financial autonomy of its members. Composed of Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa, as well as new members and strategic partners, the bloc encourages the use of national currencies and its own payment platforms, challenging the monetary hegemony of the United States. This paper analyzes this movement from the theoretical perspective of Robert Gilpin, interpreting BRICS+ de-dollarization as a response to the relative decline of the hegemonic power.

Keywords: International Order; BRICS; USA; Hegemony.

Introduction

This article analyzes the de-dollarization agenda promoted by the group of emerging economies known as BRICS+. In the context of transformations in the international order, understanding the bloc's actions, expansion, and institutionalization is essential to assess its effects on global financial, commercial, and political flows.

The initiatives within the group's de-dollarization agenda reflect the growing influence of BRICS+ in the reorganization of the international financial system and in the redistribution of global power. This research has a basic and exploratory nature and adopts a hypothetical-deductive approach of a qualitative character, based on bibliographic and documentary sources, interpreting the de-dollarization agenda as a response to the relative decline of the hegemonic power and as an attempt to redefine the rules of the global political economy.

The paper is organized into three parts. The first presents the Theory of Hegemonic Stability, according to Robert Gilpin, in order to understand the rise and decline of hegemonic powers. The second examines the "exorbitant privilege" of the dollar, addressing its rise and crises. The third analyzes the strategies of BRICS+ aimed at de-dollarization, from its formation to its most recent initiatives.

Hegemonic Stability Theory From the Perspective of Robert Gilpin

The contemporary financial order is undergoing structural transformations, driven by the redistribution of economic and political power in the international arena. To understand these changes, the contributions of political scientist Robert Gilpin are particularly relevant, especially his interpretation of the Theory of Hegemonic Stability. This approach, initially formulated by Charles Kindleberger, argues that the stability of the international economy depends on the existence of a hegemonic state capable of promoting and sustaining a relatively stable economic system.

In *The Political Economy of International Relations* (1987), Gilpin expands this perspective by arguing that the dominant power is responsible for providing international public goods, such as the supply of a reserve currency, the guarantee of security, and access to markets. In this way, hegemonic leadership contributes to the organization and maintenance of the liberal international economy.

However, according to the author, the power of hegemonies tends to decline over time due to changes in the distribution of power and the rise of new states. This process can generate instability and disputes between the dominant power and one or more emerging actors, characterizing historical cycles of rise and decline in the international system.

As the author observes, this involves a direct dispute between dominant powers and emerging challengers, which may mobilize a large portion of the states within the international system (Gilpin, 1981, p. 199). In this sense, the so-called hegemonic war is not limited to military confrontation, but also involves political, economic, and ideological dimensions, in which the established power seeks to contain or limit the ambitions of the challenging state. These moments represent decisive periods of reorganization in the international order.

The Exorbitant Privilege of the Dollar

In this context, the United States consolidated itself as the main international hegemonic power after the end of World War II, especially following the Bretton Woods Conference, in 1944, when the dollar became the main international reserve currency, initially convertible into gold (Barreto, 2009).

The country enjoys unique advantages in relation to other nations. While most countries must generate trade surpluses to accumulate reserves and meet their external obligations, the United States can pay its debt in the very currency it issues, which reduces the need for surpluses to finance international commitments. In addition, its government bonds are considered a global “safe asset,” that is, a highly reliable asset for investors and institutions (Lara, 2025), allowing the country to sustain external deficits for long periods, including during times of crisis.

However, the condition of an international reserve currency also involves disadvantages. The so-called Triffin Dilemma, formulated by Robert Triffin in 1950, points out that, in order to ensure liquidity in the international system, the country issuing the reserve currency must maintain recurring external deficits (Resende, 2024).

The predominance of the dollar also expands the ability to exert economic pressure on other states. Since many global transactions depend on the U.S. currency and on institutions connected to its financial system, Washington can restrict the access of certain states to global payments, including through networks such as SWIFT, thereby increasing the reach of its sanctions and its influence in the international system.

The economist Barry Eichengreen (2011, p.122) describes these advantages as the “exorbitant privilege,” an expression that refers to the ability of the United States to attract external resources at relatively low costs. The supremacy of the dollar is not based solely on the country’s geopolitical influence, but also on structural factors such as trust in its institutions, the depth and sophistication of its financial markets, the high global liquidity associated with the currency, and its wide acceptance in international transactions.

Since the dollar consolidated itself as the main international currency, questions have arisen regarding the durability of this position and the possibility that other currencies could share

this role. In 1960, Triffin highlighted the vulnerabilities of this arrangement (Resende, 2024). To meet the growing global demand for liquidity, the United States would need to issue increasingly larger amounts of dollars. However, this process could reduce confidence in the currency and generate instability in the international monetary system.

The so-called Triffin Dilemma highlights the tension between ensuring liquidity in the international financial system and preserving the credibility of the reserve currency. For the dollar to circulate widely, the United States tends to maintain external deficits. However, prolonged deficits may weaken confidence in the currency. The challenge, therefore, lies in balancing the supply of dollars without compromising the stability of the system.

This fragility became more evident in 1971, when U.S. President Richard Nixon suspended the convertibility of the dollar into gold, a measure that marked the practical collapse of the system established at the Bretton Woods Conference (Cunha et al., 2023). From that moment onward, currencies began to operate predominantly under floating exchange rate regimes, intensifying debates about the permanence of the dollar as the main international reserve currency.

Similar debates resurfaced in the 1980s, when the growing internationalization of currencies such as the German mark and the Japanese yen fueled expectations that they could challenge the predominance of the dollar. Later, in the 1990s, the launch of the Euro reinforced predictions that the new currency could compete with the U.S. dollar in the international monetary system (Cunha et al., 2023).

In this regard, Eichengreen (2011, p.122) highlights that the economic and military dominance of the United States, combined with the international role of the dollar, has generated tensions among different countries. The author argues that an increasingly multipolar world economy may favor the emergence of competing currencies with international recognition, although this does not necessarily imply the end of the dollar's centrality.

Another moment of intense questioning occurred during the 2008 Global Financial Crisis. Originating in the U.S. financial system, the crisis was triggered by the uncontrolled expansion of credit and the mismanagement of assets, especially in the real estate market (Martins, 2015). Its effects quickly spread throughout the international financial system, causing economic contraction and high levels of uncertainty in several regions of the world.

In sum, the dollar continues to occupy a central position as the main reserve currency and the main currency used in international trade transactions. However, episodes such as the 2008 crisis and the recurrent use of economic sanctions by the United States have reignited debates about the need for an international monetary system that is less dependent on a single currency.

BRICS+ and Its De-Dollarization Agenda

In this context of transformations in the international order, BRICS+ has consolidated itself as a relevant actor in international economic and political discussions. The group is currently composed of eleven countries: Brazil, Russia, India, China, South Africa, Saudi Arabia, Egypt, the United Arab Emirates, Ethiopia, Indonesia, and Iran. Originally, the grouping included only Brazil, Russia, India, and China and was called BRIC. The term was coined in 2001 by financial analyst Jim O'Neill in a Goldman Sachs report, highlighting the growth potential of these emerging economies (Pires, 2011).

Political coordination among these emerging countries began in 2006, during meetings held on the sidelines of the United Nations General Assembly in New York. In 2009, the first official summit took place in Yekaterinburg, Russia (Moreira and Figueira, 2014, p. 54–62). In 2011, South Africa joined the group, consolidating the acronym BRICS.

The first major expansion occurred in 2024 with the entry of Saudi Arabia, Egypt, the United Arab Emirates, Ethiopia, and Iran, at which point the coalition began to be referred to as BRICS+ (Braun, 2025). On the same occasion, during the 16th Summit held in Kazan, the category of “partner country” was created to expand dialogue and cooperation with other emerging economies, including Belarus, Bolivia, Kazakhstan, Cuba, Malaysia, Nigeria, Thailand, Uganda, Uzbekistan, and Vietnam. In 2025, Indonesia joined as a full member of the grouping.

BRICS+ has advocated changes in traditional international financial institutions such as the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Bank, seeking to expand the participation of Global South countries in international economic governance. This debate gained strength after the 2008 financial crisis, which exposed weaknesses in the global system (Uchoa, 2014). However, given the difficulty of advancing reforms within these institutions, particularly due to the stagnation of the reform process in the United States Congress since 2012, the group chose to create its own financial cooperation mechanisms.

In 2014, the New Development Bank (NDB) was established, headquartered in Shanghai, China, with the objective of financing infrastructure and development projects in emerging economies and developing countries, regardless of whether they are members of BRICS+. In the same year, the Contingent Reserve Arrangement (CRA) was also created to provide financial support to members in situations of balance of payments pressure (Pomeroy, 2014). This mechanism functions as a complementary safety net, strengthening the group's capacity to respond to external shocks.

In recent years, BRICS+ has intensified its de-dollarization agenda, particularly after the sanctions imposed by the United States on Russia, which included the freezing of international reserves and the exclusion of the country from the SWIFT network (Bordallo, 2024). The freezing of Russian assets generated distrust among several countries regarding the high level of power concentrated in the hands of the United States through the international financial system and the central role of the dollar. This scenario led BRICS members to recognize the need to adopt measures aimed at reducing dependence on the

U.S. currency (Lopes, 2024).

Other financial integration initiatives have also gained prominence, such as discussions about a common currency for the group; BRICS Pay, a platform designed to facilitate intra-bloc payments, operating in a manner similar to SWIFT (Helmy, 2025); and BRICS Bridge, a blockchain-based system that connects the central banks of member countries, providing greater security and efficiency in transactions (BRICS Bridge, 2025).

At the summit held in July 2025 in Brasília, BRICS leaders reinforced their encouragement of the use of national currencies in trade transactions within the group, a strategy aimed at reducing operational costs and strengthening trade among members (Braun, 2025). In this context, the debate on alternative financial mechanisms gained greater centrality amid external pressures on the international monetary architecture.

Also in July, the President of the United States, Donald Trump, declared that any country adhering to what he called the “anti-American policies” of BRICS would be subject to the imposition of additional tariffs of 10 percent, stating that “there will be no exceptions to this policy” (Braun, 2025). During the same period, Trump intensified his rhetoric and announced the imposition of a 50 percent tariff on Brazilian imports, to take effect on August 6, which contributed to increasing geopolitical tensions.

The measures adopted by Donald Trump tend to further encourage BRICS+ to pursue greater autonomy within the international financial system. The reaction of the U.S. president to the group can be understood in light of the weakening of the logic of dependence in negotiations traditionally mediated by the West. For Trump, the consolidation of BRICS+ expands the capacity of actors outside the sphere of influence of the United States to act more autonomously and therefore represents a threat to U.S. hegemony.

In this context, Robert Gilpin’s interpretation helps to understand the current tensions. According to the author, international hegemonies follow historical cycles; a dominant power organizes the global order according to its interests, but its relative power tends to decline as other actors grow and accumulate economic and technological capabilities. In the case of the United States, the postwar international order was structured on the basis of institutions and mechanisms that reflect this leadership, such as the IMF, the World Bank, the SWIFT network, and the country’s influence within the United Nations, among other institutions.

For Gilpin, hegemony is not sustained solely through military superiority, but also through the capacity to shape global economic rules and provide public goods, such as a currency widely used in international trade. In this sense, the dollar occupies a central role in the organization of the world economy. However, the growth of other economies and the emergence of coalitions such as BRICS+ gradually reduce the relative superiority of the hegemon, generating greater competition and tensions within the international system.

The expansion of the grouping and the strengthening of its de-dollarization agenda therefore constitute a process of contestation of the established international order. In response, the United States has mobilized different political, economic, and institutional instruments to preserve the centrality of the dollar in the international financial system. Meanwhile, the countries involved in this agenda seek to expand their financial autonomy and reduce their vulnerability to sanctions, aiming to limit the use of the dollar as an instrument of power within the international system.

The so-called hegemonic war, according to Robert Gilpin (2001), goes beyond military confrontation and also involves political, economic, and ideological dimensions. In the political dimension, BRICS+ seeks greater autonomy in international decision-making and negotiations, reducing dependence on mechanisms traditionally influenced by Western powers. In the economic dimension, competition manifests itself in attempts to expand the use of national currencies in trade transactions, as well as in the creation of alternative financial mechanisms such as BRICS Pay and BRICS Bridge, among others. In the ideological dimension, the dispute involves different visions of the international order, contrasting the maintenance of Western leadership with the defense of a more multipolar configuration of the international system.

In summary, the initiatives promoted by the group are still not sufficient to displace the status of the dollar. An additional factor limiting this process is the heterogeneity of BRICS+. Even when it was composed only of the five original members, there were already difficulties in reaching consensus on concrete measures (Lima, 2024). With the expansion to eleven countries, this challenge has become even more complex. Furthermore, the consolidation of a new world order requires more than economic and financial initiatives; it also involves the construction of narratives, political consensus, and forms of legitimacy widely recognized within the international system. In this context, the group would need to demonstrate the capacity to provide international public goods associated with the stability and predictability of the global economic order.

In this sense, the success of BRICS+ will be directly related to its ability to manage internal differences among its members and to advance in the construction of a model of multilateral governance based on equity, respect for state sovereignty, and cooperation among countries on more horizontal terms.

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